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EXIT
Exploring sustainable
strategies to counteract
territorial inequalities
from an intersectional
approach

Working Paper

Left-Behind or Moving Forward? Place-Based Responses to Territorial Disparities in Europe

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1. Introduction

Territorial inequalities are increasingly recognized as a critical challenge in achieving equitable social and economic development. These disparities manifest in various forms, including unequal access to healthcare, education, housing, employment opportunities, social services, mobility, digital inclusiveness and community resources. Territorial inequalities not only perpetuate social and economic disparities but also undermine broader societal goals such as social cohesion and sustainable development. Territories burdened by persistent inequalities often experience higher rates of poverty, social exclusion, and political disenfranchisement, creating a cycle that is challenging to break. Understanding and addressing these inequalities require nuanced approaches that consider the structural, cultural, and policy-driven factors underpinning them. Recent debates have highlighted how policies targeting rural, deprived, or so-called “left-behind” areas are frequently designed in metropolitan centres, creating a significant disconnect between policy frameworks and the lived realities of these areas (MacKinnon et al., 2022). Consequently, such policies often reflect top-down, growth-driven logics that have largely failed to deliver meaningful or lasting improvements on the ground (Hadjimichalis & Hudson, 2014; Lang & Görmar, 2019). That is, conventional approaches to tackling territorial inequalities often overlook place-based, endogenous strategies that harness local assets and capacities (Rodríguez-Pose, 2018). For policies to effectively address territorial inequalities, it is crucial to gather evidence from local communities that highlights local practices and strategies (Jubany et al, 2025).

This paper synthesizes insights from eight European contexts - Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Italy, Serbia, Spain, and the United Kingdom - to examine strategies and practices employed to mitigate territorial inequalities, reflecting on their conceptualization and application in diverse contexts, from a place-based approach. The paper is based on data gathered from a period of ethnographic research carried out in 17 designated territories across Europe, and considers this alongside findings already documented. Based on this ethnographic fieldwork, the present paper highlights different strategies identified throughout these territories.

The paper is structured as follows: Following a brief methodological note, the core of the paper summarises key comparative findings. These are organised into three thematic sections: first, an exploration of the importance of local contexts and socio-political dynamics; second, an examination of community engagement and endogenous strategies; and third, an analysis of multi-level governance and strategic coordination. The paper concludes with a synthesis of cross-cutting lessons that emerge from the case studies, offering insights into common challenges, enabling factors, and the contribution of ethnographic methods to place-sensitive policymaking.

2. Methodological note

This paper draws on ethnographic research conducted between February and September 2024 across 17 sites defined as suffering from territorial inequalities, or as ‘left-behind places’, in Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Italy, Serbia, Spain, and the United Kingdom¹. The sites—three in Spain and two in each of the other countries—were selected based on criteria developed in earlier phases of the EXIT research, particularly the heuristic model outlined in Karasz et al. (2025). In this model, ‘left-behindness’ is understood as a form of territorial inequality that emerges as a dialectic relationship between a peripheral experience in concrete locations on the one hand and political discourses as well as the place-specific indicators and employment of policy instruments on the other. This definition of ‘left-behindness’ encompasses rural, urban and post-industrial places.

Data collection involved 508 in-depth and walking interviews with a total of 538 residents and stakeholders, 21 focus groups with 80 participants, and extensive participant observation at selected sites across the areas. An intersectional approach guided both sampling and analysis, considering factors such as gender, ethnicity, age, class, and disability in order to capture compounded vulnerabilities.

By focusing on lived experiences, ethnographic research provides rich, qualitative insights into how individuals and communities experience and navigate inequalities in their daily lives. The research was structured around seven thematic areas: (1) social services and health; (2) formal and informal education; (3) employment and professional life; (4) community; (5) housing, environment, and regeneration; (6) mobility and immobility; and (7) digital inclusiveness. These themes provided a framework for analysing responses to territorial inequalities in everyday life and how they are understood by residents and local stakeholders.

¹ For an overview of the case study areas, please refer to <https://www.exit-project.eu/interactive-map/>

3. Main insights

3.1. Local contexts and socio-political dynamics

Geographical settings, historical legacies, and socio-political dynamics play a crucial role in shaping the varied strategies used to confront economic decline, social fragmentation, and deficiencies in public service provision. Local socio-economic conditions and geographical particularities are essential to understanding how marginalisation is both experienced and addressed. Across the studied territories, local context not only shapes the specific forms territorial inequalities take but also influences the responses developed by grassroots actors and institutional stakeholders alike.

In Murano, one of the Italian case studies, strategic responses are closely tied to the island's renowned glassmaking tradition and the growing pressures of tourism. Here, the challenge lies in balancing the preservation of cultural heritage with the need for economic sustainability. Similarly, in Pyrgos, Greece, residents propose to leverage the area's natural and cultural assets to strengthen the tourism sector, particularly during the summer months. One proposed initiative involves creating a cohesive strategy that links local attractions—such as wineries and coastal sites—to attract visitors and foster economic development.

In the UK, the cases of Stoke-on-Trent and Rochdale illustrate how distinct historical, geographical, and political contexts shape strategic orientations within the same national framework. Stoke-on-Trent's strategy is rooted in its industrial past—embodied in its "pits and pots" identity—and shaped by its geographical position between Manchester and Birmingham. The city emphasises grassroots initiatives and the revitalisation of its industrial heritage as tools for strengthening local identity and promoting economic renewal. In contrast, Rochdale navigates its location within the Greater Manchester metropolitan area by pursuing systemic reform and regional integration. Its approach seeks to align local priorities with broader metropolitan governance structures while addressing persistent local challenges. Both towns are also affected by wider media narratives and political developments. In Stoke, populist discourse targeting immigrant communities complicates efforts to build social cohesion. In Rochdale, misinformation undermines public trust and hampers collective action. Nonetheless, both contexts reveal the potential of strategic media campaigns, political advocacy, and the mobilisation of historical legacies to support more inclusive and sustainable development.

3.2. Community engagement and endogenous strategies

Locally embedded actors and grassroots organizations play a critical role in initiating responses tailored to territorial needs. NGO and grassroots strategies tend to be developed in response to unmet local needs, thus filling the gaps in local public services. These strategies rely on local knowledge and voluntary participation.

To illustrate, the Danish area of Morsø has a neo-endogenous development model that focuses on community-driven initiatives and leveraging local resources and networks, showing the highest levels of voluntary activity in Denmark. Grassroots organizations and resident volunteers actively maintain local institutions such as schools and community centers, ensuring grassroots mobilisation to bridge gaps in external support. The municipality thus prioritises the use of local resources by fostering collective efforts, rooted in Denmark's cooperative movement. For instance, residents have successfully lobbied for grants and training programs to fund community projects.

Residents' explicit recognition of territorial inequalities can serve as a powerful catalyst for collective action to address unmet needs. In the Italian area of Gennargentu, for instance, the SOS Barbagia-Mandrolisai Healthcare Committee mobilises local communities to demand improved access to healthcare services. In Murano, the MammeXMurano initiative emerged in response to the dismantling of municipal powers, aiming to preserve essential community services through grassroots engagement. In Gennargentu, a feminist collective has played a key role in making visible how healthcare-related territorial inequalities disproportionately impact women—particularly in areas such as maternal health and caregiving. The absence of accessible gynecological services forces women to travel long distances for routine check-ups, a burden further intensified by their caregiving responsibilities. This collective has been vocal in advocating for local healthcare services that account for gender-specific needs, contributing a nuanced, intersectional perspective to efforts aimed at counteracting inequalities in the region.

Also in the Greek case study areas, resilience is demonstrated through grassroots initiatives, community-led projects, and informal networks that step in where institutional support is lacking. For example, flooding is common in Acharnes, where infrastructural deficiencies such as inadequate drainage systems, have yet to be systematically addressed by municipal authorities. In the absence of consistent state intervention, residents take individual initiatives to maintain their properties and implement makeshift solutions to flooding and related environmental problems. These informal, locally driven responses underscore the community's capacity for self-organisation and adaptive problem-solving, even under constrained conditions.

Further, in smaller places, positionalities and roles often overlap in local informal networks. Stakeholders and professionals tend to be residents themselves, and it is common for one individual to hold multiple roles within the local social and economic system. The same person might serve in the local government, participate as an active board member in local associations, and hold a professional position in the field of social services or as an employer. This overlap can be an advantage, as these actors are well connected and able to respond quickly or activate support networks for people in need. However, falling out of favour with such a local key actor can lead to significant negative consequences, as shown in one of the Austrian case studies, where a stakeholder pointed out that anonymity doesn't exist in their small community.

Nevertheless, newcomers and members of minority and migrant communities often lack access to these informal local networks, which can thus have an exclusionary effect. In Spain, such networks are frequently organized through neighbourhood associations, as seen in Montcada i Reixac. One example is a local association that has actively campaigned against the conversion of a cement factory into an incinerator on the edge of the neighbourhood—an effort that has recently seen some success. These associations often build on the efforts of a few highly involved members volunteering their time. Stakeholders and residents involved report a growing sense that the associations are expected to cover too many needs, without sufficient participation to effectively address them. At the same time, many associations struggle to attract residents with migrant backgrounds. Migrant residents interviewed pointed to more urgent concerns in their daily lives, whilst noting that previous efforts to build connections between international migrants and long-term Spanish residents have largely failed. This was attributed to a lack of generational continuity and the frequent mobility of migrant residents, driven by precarious living conditions and limited resources. Moreover, the issues prioritized by long-term residents within these associations may not reflect the most pressing concerns of migrant residents—many of whom may not be able to remain in the area long enough to benefit from or invest in such local initiatives. However, cause-driven associations and efforts to build networks beyond the local level are experienced as more engaging and relevant to younger and migrant residents, who report that they connect more with shared objectives across different territories than historical local narratives and causes.

Addressing territorial inequality requires not only financial resources but also genuine community involvement. Strategies put forward need to actively involve a diversity of residents and other stakeholders at the local level. In this regard, it is important to identify existing approaches of endogenous developments, highlighting how they can be strengthened, while remaining mindful of local power structures that may exclude certain residents or groups.

3.3. Multi-level governance and strategic coordination

Strategies that succeed often involve coordination across local, regional, and national actors, though effectiveness varies depending on the alignment and communication between levels. Collaboration between local actors and policymakers is essential to address systemic challenges. In several contexts, strategic initiatives have benefited from alignment across governance tiers, though the outcomes vary. In Italy, the Murano geothermal project, part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), exemplifies an ambitious attempt to connect environmental and economic goals. However, it faced political hurdles with a lack of collaboration at the municipal level, which in the end deterred its implementation. In contrast, Gennargentu-Mandrolisai demonstrates a more fluid collaboration between actors and levels, with youth councils and local schools working together to promote digital literacy, suggesting that horizontal coordination can result in tangible social benefits. Nevertheless, interactions with policymakers are often limited to project approvals or funding negotiations, missing opportunities for sustained dialogue and co-creation.

Similarly, in the UK, the effectiveness of strategies depends on collaborative efforts involving local councils, community organisations, and national stakeholders. Exemplified by the area of Rochdale, the complexity of metropolitan governance can impede coordination, yet it also enables scaled inclusion when actors at different levels manage to collaborate effectively.

A recurring pattern across countries is the need to balance top-down institutional support with bottom-up initiatives. In Spain (Montcada i Reixac), the sustainability of local strategies depends on the interplay between motivated individuals, institutional backing, and generational renewal. This is also shown in the Italian case studies, which highlight how effective responses emerge from the intersection of individual, group, and institutional efforts, where local actors combine community-driven initiatives with institutional frameworks. For example, Murano's grassroots organisations collaborate with the Venice municipality, which provides free spaces for activities. In Gennargentu-Mandrolisai, the National Strategy for Inner Areas (NSIA) supports infrastructure and digital inclusion projects, such as broadband expansion and telemedicine services. In line with this, the Austrian cases highlight that locally rooted initiatives and NGOs tend to have a greater impact on the population and are felt to be more effective in addressing territorial inequalities. In contrast, actors and organisations that engage with the region only periodically to deliver specific services are not as positively valued by residents and local stakeholders.

The need for hybrid approaches also appears in the Serbian municipalities of Golubac and Surdulica, where the gap between long-term policy visions and residents' immediate needs is pronounced. While national and regional actors prioritise structural reforms such as infrastructure or industry diversification, local communities demand more immediate improvements—better healthcare, jobs, housing, and environmental conditions. The disconnect illustrates the difficulty of synchronising strategic timelines and expectations across governance levels.

Finally, resource distribution between urban and rural areas also shapes how multi-level coordination plays out. In Belgium, the predominance of urban-centric policies limits the equity of rural development strategies. Public authorities often justify urban investment on the grounds of demographic reach, yet this leaves rural areas with reduced services and fewer implementation resources. Even when private and institutional actors attempt to compensate—particularly around rural mobility—most schemes remain focused on enhancing urban connectivity rather than addressing rural exclusion. This is also felt in the rural Catalan Pyrenees, where associations and cooperatives for the provision of services have appeared as an alternative to the lack of coverage of public services across territories. As a stakeholder involved in a rural association in Catalonia, Spain, highlighted: *“The entire structure has been designed with an urban logic, and we don't count, we are an expense, we are few and we are not profitable”* (ES-A2a-IV-SH8).

4. Conclusion: Cross-cutting lessons

The comparative analysis of strategies across diverse territorial contexts reveals several recurring lessons that are essential for designing effective and equitable responses to spatial inequalities. These insights highlight both the importance of situated knowledge and the value of multi-level, adaptive governance.

Strong community involvement consistently emerges as a foundation for legitimacy and long-term effectiveness. Locally driven initiatives harness social capital, foster trust, and are often better attuned to real local needs. However, their sustainability can be threatened by exclusionary practices, uneven participation, or the over-reliance on a small group of committed individuals—raising concerns about burnout and representativeness.

Strategies must be carefully adapted to local histories, economic structures, and demographic profiles. Rigid policy models often miss the nuances of place-specific challenges and opportunities, undermining both effectiveness and community buy-in. Hybrid approaches that combine top-down resources and institutional support with bottom-up initiative and local knowledge tend to produce more resilient and sustainable solutions. These blended models can more effectively navigate tensions between long-term structural change and the urgency of everyday needs

Successful interventions tend to be those where local, regional, and national actors are not only coordinated but engaged in meaningful feedback loops. Ethnographic insights can play a key role here by informing higher-level policy with grounded, context-sensitive knowledge, helping to bridge gaps between strategic planning and lived realities. By capturing voices, experiences, and informal practices, ethnography reveals both the shortcomings of dominant policy narratives and the potential for alternative, community-rooted pathways forward.

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